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Empirical Analysis Of The Effect Of Tax Mix On Price To Earnings Ratio: The Nigerian Industrial Goods Firms Experience

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of tax mix on price to earnings ratio of industrial goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group from 2014 to 2023. The independent variable of the study, tax mix, was proxied by withholding tax and value added tax, while the dependent variable was price earnings ratio. The research design adopted for this study was ex post facto. Secondary data were used and the population of the study was 13 listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The sample size of this study was 11 industrial goods firms which were purposively selected. The robust least square regression technique was used in analysing the data and the statistical software employed was STATA 14. The results of the analysis revealed that withholding tax has non-statistically significant effect on price to earnings ratio while value added tax has significant negative effect on price to earnings ratio of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that tax mix has significant effect on price to earnings ratio of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. It was therefore recommended that policymakers should simplify withholding tax procedures to further reduce administrative burdens on firms without impacting their valuation. It was also recommended that the government should evaluate the VAT structure to minimize its adverse impact on businesses, especially in highly taxed industries.

Keywords: Tax mix, withholding tax, value added tax, price to earnings ratio, firms' value

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Tax mix, which refers to the combination of different taxes levied by government, can have a significant impact on a firm's price-earnings ratio (P/E ratio) and, consequently, its market value. The strategic decisions made by companies in relation to tax payment does not only impact the firms' profitability, cost structure and cash flow but also affect the ways that market and investors react to these activities. A firm's tax mix, encompassing various forms of taxation such as withholding tax (WHT) and value-added tax (VAT), represents a critical element in this dynamic. The concept of firm value is central to financial management, as it reflects the market's perception of a company's future earning potential and overall performance. Among the various measures of firm value, the price-to-earnings (P/E) ratio is widely recognized as an essential indicator.

Withholding tax is an advance payment of income tax, and is deductible at source on payments made for certain transactions. According to Zik-Rullahi and Abubakar (2024), it is a type of tax deducted at source from income earned by individuals or companies on tax bases typified by the extant laws of the land. Withholding tax is a critical component of the tax system designed to ensure the timely collection of taxes and promote compliance. A higher withholding tax rate can reduce the attractiveness of investing in a particular country, potentially leading to lower foreign investment and a depressed P/E ratio for firms in that country. In Nigeria, WHT rates range from 5% to 10%. WHT can reduce a firm's cash flows, increase its tax burden, and potentially decrease its earnings. Value Added Tax (VAT) is a consumption tax levied at each stage of the consumption chain and borne by the final consumer of the product or service (Odunsi, 2022). It is levied on any individual, body corporate or organization that consumes, procures or imports taxable goods or services (Okonkwo & Onodugo, 2019). VAT can increase the cost of goods and services, reduce demand, and potentially decrease a firm's earnings.

The P/E ratio highlights the relationship between a company's stock price and its earnings per share, serving as a critical benchmark for investors and financial analysts in evaluating a firm's growth prospects and investment attractiveness (Latrous, 2019). The price-earnings (P/E) ratio is a widely used metric for evaluating a firm's value. It represents the amount investors are willing to pay for each unit of earnings. A higher P/E ratio indicates a higher valuation of the firm. However, taxation can impact a firm's earnings and, consequently, its P/E ratio. Withholding tax impacts firms directly by reducing their earnings through mandatory deductions on dividends, interests, or other payments, while VAT primarily influences the cost of goods sold and overall operational efficiency. Both taxes interact with a firm's profitability and investment attractiveness, thus affecting its valuation metrics, including the P/E ratio.

While corporate taxes are necessary for funding government activities, they represent a significant financial burden for firms, directly reducing the resources available for reinvestment, innovation, and shareholder distribution. High or poorly managed tax obligations can diminish a firm's profitability, limit its growth potential, and ultimately reduce its market value. Existing studies on taxation and firm value have predominantly focused on broad measures of tax policy, with limited attention to the individual effects of withholding tax and VAT on the P/E ratio of firms, especially in the Nigerian industrial goods sector. Another major gap identified in the literature was that different periods were studied (Abiola et al., 2022; Eneisik et al., 2023; Owoniya & Olaoye, 2022). In addition to this, other measures of tax mix such as petroleum profit tax, custom and excise duties, stamp duties, company income tax, education and capital gains tax were used other than the ones used in this study. Another notable gap found in the literature was that most of these studies focused on the effect of tax mix on profitability and gross domestic product (GDP) as if these taxes have no effect on firms' value. Based on these gaps, this study was undertaken to ascertain the effect of tax mix on price earnings ratio of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature review and hypotheses development

Tax mix

Tax mix refers to the composition and proportion of various types of taxes that a corporate firm is subject to. This mix can include taxes such as withholding tax, value added tax, corporate income tax, sales tax, property tax, payroll tax, and others. Researchers such as (Savka & Radojka, 2013; Iormbagah et al., 2020) who have written on corporate taxes focused their studies on one or the other aspects of corporate taxes; ranging from corporate income tax to deferred tax and tax incentives. This has streamlined the knowledge of most readers to think each aspect of corporate tax is in its' sense mutual of the other, which in most cases if tax burdens from corporate income tax become high, failure on corporate managers to explore other aspects of corporate tax as a result of limited knowledge leads to a possibility of tax evasion. Tax mix pertains the various taxes that are available to be explored (Sabbar & Sabri, 2021). Nwaeke et al., (2022) stated that tax mix can further be divided into personal tax mix for individuals and corporate tax mix for firms. Tax mix has a direct impact on a firm's firm value due to its influence on

profitability, cash flow, and overall tax burden (Olusegun, & Nwoko, 2018). Tax mix in this study is viewed in terms of withholding tax and value added tax in this study.

Price to earnings ratio

The price-to-earnings (P/E) ratio is a financial metric widely used in the context of corporate firms to assess the relative value of a company's stock. It reflects the relationship between a company's stock price and its earnings per share (EPS). The P/E ratio is calculated by dividing the market price per share of a company's stock by its earnings per share (EPS). It provides a measure of how much investors are willing to pay for each kobo of the company's earnings (Oyedokun & Adegbe, 2020). The P/E ratio is often seen as an indicator of a company's valuation. A higher P/E ratio typically indicates that investors have high expectations for the company's future earnings growth. Conversely, a lower P/E ratio may suggest that the market has lower expectations for future prospects. The P/E ratio is frequently used to compare a company's valuation with its peers or competitors within the same industry. This allows investors to gauge whether a stock is relatively overvalued or undervalued compared to similar companies.

Withholding tax and price earning ratio

Withholding tax is an advance income tax payment which is intended to bring taxpayers such as consultants, contractors, suppliers, landlords, and shareholders into the tax net. Withholding tax (WHT) can affect the market value of firms in several ways, depending on the context and stakeholders involved. According to Zik-Rullahi and Abubakar (2024), it is a type of tax deducted at source from income earned by individuals or companies on tax bases typified by the extant laws of the land. Withholding tax is a critical component of the tax system designed to ensure the timely collection of taxes and promote compliance. The primary aim of withholding tax is to streamline the tax collection process, reducing the risk of tax evasion and ensuring that tax liabilities are met as income is earned (Afolabi, 2020)). By deducting tax at the source, withholding tax helps to smooth the flow of government revenue and reduces the administrative burden on tax authorities. Withholding tax is on specified transactions and this transactions and their current withholding tax rates in Nigeria are dividend, interest and rents (10%); directors fees (10 %), hire of equipment (10%); royalties (10%), commission, consultancy, technical service fees (10%); construction (2.5%); management fees (10%)and contracts (5%). The penalties for failure to deduct or remit is 10 of the amounts not deducted/remitted. WHT reduces the net dividends received by shareholders, which can make the stock less attractive, especially for investors focused on dividend income. Lower attractiveness can put downward pressure on the market value. According to Zik-Rullahi, and Abubakar (2024), if WHT on dividends is high, investors might prefer capital gains over dividend payments, influencing how firms structure payouts and potentially affecting valuation. Firms paying WHT on behalf of foreign shareholders or contractors might experience a cash outflow, reducing available funds for reinvestment, growth, or other value-enhancing activities. This could impact investor perception of future profitability and growth potential, thus affecting market value. Firms with high WHT compliance costs or those perceived as less tax-efficient may be valued lower due to perceived inefficiencies or risks of penalties.

Conversely, firms that manage WHT effectively might improve investor confidence and market value. Inconsistent or high WHT rates in a jurisdiction may deter foreign investment, reducing demand for stocks of firms operating in such regions and lowering their market value Ogbonna et al. (2020). Policy clarity around WHT can also affect the valuation positively if it reduces uncertainty. For sectors with substantial cross-border activities, WHT on royalties, services, or interest might be significant, directly impacting cash flow and valuation. Obi et al (2018) noted that domestic sectors with lower exposure to WHT may experience a lesser impact on their market value. Withholding tax can influence the market value of firms through its effect on shareholder returns, cash flows, compliance costs, and investor perceptions. However, the extent of the impact depends on tax policy, firm strategies, and investor preferences. From empirical studies Zik-Rullahi and Abubakar (2024) found insignificant effect of withholding tax while Ogbonna et al found that withholding tax has significant negative effect on firms' value when measured using market capitalization. On the other hand, Obi et al. (2018) documented a

positive relationship between withholding tax and market value of firms in Nigeria. Based on these findings, this study hypothesized that;

Ho₁: Withholding tax does not have any significant effect on price to earnings ratio of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

Value added tax and firm value

VAT is a consumption tax that applies to goods and services, indirectly impacting firm value. A higher VAT rate can increase product prices, which might reduce demand, especially for price-sensitive products. According to Eneisik et al. (2023) lower demand translates to lower sales revenue and, ultimately, lower firm value. However, the impact varies by industry; essential goods may see minimal demand changes, while luxury or non-essential goods may experience a more pronounced decline. Businesses can often reclaim VAT on their inputs, reducing the net VAT impact on their cost structure. For firms that are able to fully reclaim input VAT, the tax does not significantly impact profitability. However, firms operating in sectors where VAT on inputs cannot be fully recovered, such as financial services, may experience reduced profitability. VAT requires firms to remit tax at each stage of the supply chain (Latrous, 2019). This can create timing issues if a firm must pay VAT before receiving payment from customers, impacting cash flow and liquidity. For firms with substantial working capital needs, this timing issue can constrain cash flow, potentially reducing firm value. Efficient cash flow management can help mitigate this effect. VAT can affect a firm's pricing strategy. Firms may attempt to pass VAT costs to consumers, but in highly competitive markets, this may not be feasible without losing market share. If firms absorb VAT to maintain competitive prices, their profit margins may decrease, impacting firm value.

The flexibility in pricing strategy and the firm's market position influence how VAT ultimately affects value (Sweetwilliams et al., 2023). Oto and Wayas (2024) found that VAT revenue accounts for a significant variation in total revenue in Nigeria; Cole et al. (2021) found a positive and significant relationship between value added tax and economic growth in Nigeria. On the other hand Lyndon and Paymaster (2020) value-added tax had positive and insignificant impact on economic growth; Alpheaus et al. (2024) found negative relationship between VAT and firms profitability. Based on these diverse findings, this study hypothesized that;

Ho₂: Value added tax does not have any significant effect on price to earnings ratio of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

2.2 Theoretical framework

Various theories have been used in the literature to support the studies on corporate tax and firms' value. But this study focused on tax planning theory. According to Hoffman (1961) tax planning activities are desirable to the extent that they reduce taxable income to the barest minimum, without sacrificing accounting income. The theory is premised on the fact that firms tax liability is based on taxable income rather than accounting income. The idea is thus to intensify activities that reduce taxable income but has no indirect relationship on accounting profit. The theory thus recognized a positive association between firm tax planning activity and firm performance.

Hoffman (1961) also recognized the role of tax cost in the tax planning activities. The theory thus provided that the positive association between tax planning and corporate performance is on a basic assumption that tax benefits from the tax planning exceed tax cost. The scope of the Hoffman's tax planning theory does not address the dynamics of tax planning and market performance. As capital markets develop and the separation of ownership and control of corporate bodies become well-spread, the need for a comprehensive tax planning theory becomes expedient. Accordingly, Hoffmann (1961) noted that since taxation are mostly based on business or accounting concepts, thus a firm can modify such activities towards the attainment of reduction in tax liability. Hoffmann identified some ambiguity and loopholes in tax laws due to unclear intentions of the legislators and concluded that successful tax schemes work with the legal concepts and precise wording of the statute and complying with these

concepts very precisely as it relates to individual firm tends to be advantageous to firms in form of tax savings.

Empirical reviews

Oto and Wayas (2024) empirically examined the relationship between value added tax and economic growth of Nigeria. Time series data on Value Added Tax (VAT) revenue, Total (Federal Government) Revenue (TR), Total (Federal Government) Expenditure (TE) and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from 2003 to 2022 sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) were analysed, using both simple regression analysis and descriptive statistical method. Findings showed that VAT revenue accounts for a significant variation in TR, TE and GDP in Nigeria. A very significant and positive correlation also exist between VAT revenue and TE. Alpheaus et al. (2024) examined the effect of corporate taxes on the profitability of selected listed food and beverage firms in Nigeria from 2013 to 2022 using secondary data which were sourced from the annual report of the selected food and beverages firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. The study employed Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) regression analysis as the estimation technique. The study found that company income tax and capital gains tax have a significant and positive effect on return on equity. However, education tax has a significant but negative effect on ROE.

Eneisik et al. (2023) empirically ascertains the effect of company's income tax on financial performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Findings showed that company income tax had a negative and insignificant effect on net profit margin of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Capital gains tax had positive and significant effect on net profit margin of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Tertiary education taxes had negative and insignificant effect on net profit margin of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Equally, Erasmus et al. (2023) empirically ascertained the effect of company's income tax on profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study adopted purposive sampling techniques to select thirty quoted manufacturing companies as a sample size from 2006-2020 and analysed using panel least squares regression. Findings showed that while company income tax and tertiary education tax had a negative and insignificant effect on net profit margin, capital gains tax had positive and significant effect on net profit margin of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Abiola et al. (2022) analyzed the influence of Company Income Tax on Firms' Profitability in the consumer goods sector of the Nigerian economy. The study employed secondary data obtained from the published financial statements of the fifteen (15) selected consumer goods company quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) for the period of 2012 to 2018. A Panel Fully Modified Ordinary Least Square was adopted in analyzing the collected data and the result from the analysis indicated that company income tax has a positive and significant influence on profit after tax in consumer goods sector of the economy. Owoniya and Olaoye (2022) examined the impact of company income tax on profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Result revealed that effective tax rate exerts insignificant negative impact on earnings per share, with reported coefficient estimate of $-0.0223004(p=0.209 > 0.05)$. Cole et al. (2021) investigated relationship between Value Added Tax (VAT) and economic growth in Nigeria from 2004 to 2018. Secondary data obtained from both Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) were used for the study, while regression analysis was used to analyze the data obtained. The results showed a positive and significant relationship between value added tax and economic growth in Nigeria. The study recommended that value added tax (VAT) should be sustained and all identified loopholes should be covered for VAT revenue to continue to contribute more significantly to economic growth in Nigeria.

Lyndon and Paymaster (2020) examined the impact of companies' income tax, value-added tax on economic growth (proxy by gross domestic product) in Nigeria. Secondary time series panel data was collected for the period 2005 to 2018 from the Statistical Bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). The study employed ordinary least squares (OLS) technique based on the computer software Windows SPSS 20 version for the analysis of data, where gross domestic product (GDP), was regressed on

company income tax (CIT) and value-added tax (VAT). The results showed that both company income tax and value-added tax had positive and significant impact on economic growth.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study was ex post facto and this design was suitable for this study because the data used were historical data obtained from the annual financial reports of industrial goods firms listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group. The population of this study consisted of all industrial goods companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NXG). As of December 31st, 2023, the total number of industrial goods firms in Nigeria were thirteen (13). The sample size of this study was 11 (eleven) industrial goods firms purposively selected. Data used in this study were secondary and ordinary least square regression analysis was used to analyze the data with STATA 14 statistical software. The model for this study was adapted from the work of Erasmus et al. (2023) and modified to suit our study. The econometric function of the model is given below:

$$FV = f(CTM)$$

$$P/E_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 WHT_{it} + \beta_2 VAT_{it} + \beta_3 OCF_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where:

FV = Firm value

CTM = Corporate tax mix

P/E = Price to earning ratio

CIT = Company income tax

EDT = Education tax

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Regression coefficients.

μ = error term

Analysis and discussion

Table 1 Descriptive statistics of tax mix and firm value of listed industrial goods firms

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
pe	110	863.322	2361.639	-125.62	172852.23
vat (N'000)	110	810023.65	2356338.6	108	16322000
wht (N'000)	110	2049654.3	7871754	101	64647000
mps	110	32.614	63.371	.33	319.9
numberofshares (N'000)	110	29333512	82936228	42640	2.898e+08
CFO (N'000)	110	536385346	162910824	-7122801	5930736

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of all variables as well as some additional variables used in this study. For the dependent proxy; price to earnings ratio (pe), lowest was -125 times. On average, companies in the industrial goods sector usually have their price earnings ratio to be about 863 times. These had standard deviation of 2362 which shows high degree of variability or difference in the dataset, implying that each price-to-earnings ratio were very different from each other and most were far from the mean. Furthermore, for the tax at source; withholding tax (wht) had a minimum of N101, meaning that that is the lowest amount of money a company ever paid in withholding taxes between 2014 to 2023. The highest withholding tax ever paid in the study period was N64,647,000 with an average and standard

deviation of N2,049,654.30 and N7,871,754 respectively. These showed a normal level of variability as the standard deviation was not too far from the mean. For the additional variables, most of which were used to compute the dependent variable. The first being market price per share (mps) showed 33 kobo to be the lowest market price per share in the sector. The highest market price per share in the industrial goods sector within 2014 to 2023 was N319.9. The statistics show that the average industrial goods firm has a market price of about N32.61. The share prices have a standard deviation of 63.37 showing high level of variability in the share prices of the firms. For number of shares, the lowest weighted average number of ordinary shares was 42640, highest was 289,800,000 shares. On average, firms in the industrial goods sector have 29,333,512 in unit of shares with a standard deviation of 82,936,228 showing a very high level of variability in the weighted average number of ordinary shares. Also, looking at the average, if this was a measure of firm size, then the sector would be characterized by relatively large firms.

Table 2 Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
pe	110	0.328	60.053	9.132	0.000
lvat	110	0.961	3.489	2.785	0.003
lwht	110	0.924	6.754	4.260	0.000
lcfo	110	0.935	5.024	3.565	0.000

Source: Researcher's computation (2024)

From table 2 above, it was observed that none of the study variables followed a normal distribution as all prob>z values were less than 0.05 level of significance and so, all null hypotheses were rejected.

Table 3 Regression results

	(1) ols pe	(2) re pe	(3) ro pe
lvat	-437.143 (0.476)	-437.143 (0.474)	-437.143** (0.025)
lwht	385.011 (0.506)	385.011 (0.505)	385.011 (0.219)
lcfo	209.647 (0.791)	209.647 (0.790)	209.647 (0.646)
Constant	4835.792** (0.021)	4835.792** (0.019)	4835.792*** (0.006)
R ²	0.122	0.163	0.231
N	110.000	110.000	110.000
F/W-Stat	2.042	10.212	17.920
p	0.088	0.075	0.007
hettest	52.44(0.000)		
vif	5.26		
LM test	0.00(1.000)		

p-values in parentheses

* *p* < 0.10, ** *p* < 0.05, *** *p* < 0.01

Researcher's compilation (2024)

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Withholding tax and price to earnings ratio

From the regression results in table 3, withholding tax has a coefficient and p values of 385.011 and 0.219 respectively. These approved the acceptance of the null hypothesis implying that withholding tax has no significant effect on the price to earnings ratio of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. This means that there exists a positive relationship between withholding tax and price to earnings ratio but there was no sufficient evidence to support this relationship. Possible reason for this is that withholding tax may not constitute a substantial proportion of the overall tax burden or financial obligations of industrial goods firms, making its impact relatively small in the broader context of profitability and valuation. Firms in this sector often face larger cost components, such as raw materials, logistics, and corporate income tax, which could overshadow the influence of withholding tax on their financial performance and investor perceptions.

Another reason could be that investors might view withholding tax as a pass-through tax that ultimately affects shareholders or other stakeholders, rather than the firm itself. For example, withholding tax on dividends affects shareholders' returns but does not necessarily influence the firm's profitability or valuation directly. As a result, withholding tax may not play a significant role in shaping market perceptions or the P/E ratio of industrial goods firms. This finding is contrary to that of Abiola et al. (2022) which found that if WHT on dividends is high, investors might prefer capital gains over dividend payments, influencing how firms structure payouts and potentially affecting valuation. According to Owoniya and Olaoye (2022), inconsistent or high withholding tax rates in a jurisdiction may deter foreign investment, reducing demand for stocks of firms operating in such regions and lowering their market value. Now, all these indicated significant relationships.

Value added tax and price to earnings ratio

Output from the robust regression model in table 3 shows that VAT had a coefficient and p value of -437.143 and 0.025. It is evident that the p-value was significant at the 5% level. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and alternate hypothesis was accepted. This indicates that value added tax (VAT) has a significant effect on price to earnings ratio of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. This implies that increase in value added taxes causes decrease in price to earnings ratio of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. In other words, the higher the value added taxes, the lower the price to earnings ratio of the firms under study. The plausible reason for this could be that, value added tax is a consumption-based tax that increases the cost of goods and services for end consumers. For firms in the industrial goods sector, higher VAT rates may lead to reduced consumer purchasing power and lower demand for their products. This decline in sales directly affects revenue and profitability, which are critical components of earnings used to calculate the P/E ratio. With declining earnings, the P/E ratio falls unless market valuations adjust proportionally, reflecting the negative effect of VAT.

In support of this finding, Eneisik et al. (2023) asserted that higher VAT increases product prices, reducing demand and sales revenue, especially for non-essential goods. This aligns with your finding of a negative effect on price-to-earnings ratios, as reduced revenue directly affects profitability and valuation. Oto and Wayas (2024) also discussed how VAT remittance timing can strain cash flow, particularly for firms needing significant working capital. This supports your reasoning that cash flow issues due to VAT can impact firm value. Contrary to this finding is Erasmus et al. (2023) who highlighted that competitive markets might prevent firms from passing VAT costs to consumers, which could moderate the negative impact on firm value if firms absorb the tax without significantly affecting consumer demand.

CONCLUSION

This highlighted the need for a balanced and efficient tax system that not only generates government revenue but also minimizes adverse consequences for firms. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that tax mix has significant effect on price earnings ratio of listed industrial goods firms in

Nigeria. It was therefore recommended that policymakers and the management of listed industrial goods firms should consider simplifying withholding tax procedures to further reduce administrative burdens on firms without impacting their valuation. Since VAT has a significant negative effect on firms' value, it was recommended that the government evaluate the VAT structure to minimize its adverse impact on businesses, especially in highly taxed industries.

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